

MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND THE CONSTITUTION OF NITROSO-PENTAMMINE COBALT SALTS

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In view of the conflicting values of the magnetic moment of nitroso-pentammine cobalt chloride (black) reported by different investigators, the susceptibility value of this substance, as well as that of its isomeric red complex, was redetermined on very carefully prepared specimens. The black chloride gave a paramagnetic moment of 1.5 Bohr magnetons, whereas the red nitrate was diamagnetic as already reported by previous workers. The value for the black chloride was somewhat lower than that obtained by Milward and co-workers (1.66 Bohr). On the basis of Pauling's structure for NO-molecule with a three electron bond, $N\equiv O$, it has been suggested that the black nitroso-pentammine cobalt complex is an equilibrium mixture of the normal and the excited states of the sixfold, octahedral, penetration complex of bivalent cobalt.

The spin of the promoted electron in such a complex with hybrid d^3-s-p^3 bonds may be either parallel or antiparallel to that of the odd electron in the three electron bond of the NO-molecule, representing the normal and the excited state of the molecule respectively. The former corresponds to a triplet paramagnetic state and the latter to a singlet diamagnetic one. This view satisfactorily accounts for the observed magnetic moment. The idea of resonance between a univalent and a trivalent cobalt atom, as put forward by Milward and co-workers, has been shown to be untenable. The red isomer has been proved to contain trivalent cobalt with a monomeric formula as previously shown by Milward and co-workers.

The constitution of the two series (black and red) of isomeric nitroso-pentammine cobalt complex, $[(H_2N)_5Co.N(O)]X_2$, has been the subject of much discussion by several workers since their preparation by Sand and Gensler (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2083; *Annalen*, 1903, 329, 194). Of these the black variety is rather unstable and passes readily with partial decomposition into the stable red modification. The black salts are immediately decomposed by acids and bases with formation of NH_3 , NO and cobaltous salts, while the red compounds are not attacked by water and dilute acids. With concentrated HCl or HBr, however, the red salts give chloro- or bromo-pentammine cobaltic salts under conditions, which do not permit of any probable oxidation. Werner and Karrer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1918, 1, 54) studied these compounds more thoroughly and concluded that in the black salts cobalt is present in the bivalent state, whereas in the red forms it is trivalent with NO behaving as a hyponitrite acid radical $(N_2O_2)^-$, though no free hyponitrous acid could be isolated. Rây and Bhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 497), from a measurement of the magnetic susceptibility of the black chloride and the red nitrate, came to the same conclusion; because they found the former paramagnetic, resembling all cobaltous compounds, and the latter diamagnetic like all cobaltic complexes. The authors, therefore, assumed after Werner and Karrer that in the red salts the NO-group is present as an anion of hyponitrous acid serving as a bridge between two trivalent cobalt atoms and giving rise to a dimeric formula,

A detailed discussion about the structure of the black series, possessing obviously a simple or monomeric formula, was not given by the authors as the specimen employed for susceptibility measurements was not believed to be magnetically pure. They simply suggested the possibility of the black salts being an equilibrium mixture.

Since the development of the quantum mechanical theory of valency much interest has centred round the structure of the stable odd molecule NO with an uneven number of electrons

and of the various types of complex compounds containing this molecule, such as nitroso-carbonyls, nitroprusside, salts of chloro- and aquo-nitroso-ruthenium amines besides the substances under discussion.

Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 3225) has shown that the normal state of NO-molecule is best represented by a structure with a three electron bond, such as $\text{:N}\equiv\ddot{\text{O}}\text{:}$, resulting from resonance or interaction between $\text{:}\ddot{\text{N}}\text{:}\ddot{\text{O}}\text{:}$ and $\text{:}\ddot{\text{N}}\text{:}\ddot{\text{O}}\text{:}^+$. A three electron bond is shown to have half the strength of a single bond. The properties of the molecule, notably its paramagnetic susceptibility, dipole moment, stability and the internuclear distance, which lie between those for double and triple bonds, are best accounted for on this view. But he found it rather difficult to give a satisfactory representation of the structure of the black nitroso-pentamine cobalt salts on this basis. This was mainly due to the fact that he assumed the cobalt atom to be trivalent in the black salts.

Milward, Wardlaw and Way (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 233) have made a very careful measurement of the susceptibilities of these two isomeric complexes and have obtained a moment value of practically 1.73 Bohr magnetons for the black chloride, and a diamagnetic χ_g -value of -0.11×10^{-6} and -0.19×10^{-6} for the red nitrate in fair agreement with that given by Rây and Bhar.

Soon after and almost simultaneously Fraser and Long (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 462) determined the susceptibility of the black chloride. The χ_g -value obtained by them (23.1×10^{-6}) gives a magnetic moment of about 3.65 Bohr magnetons for the cobalt atom, rather a very high value compared with that of Milward and co-workers.

It was, therefore, considered desirable to repeat the measurement on the perfectly pure specimens of these two interesting compounds. Details of the preparation and measurement are given below in the experimental part. A value of about 1.5 Bohr magnetons was found for the black chloride. For the red nitrate a diamagnetic gram susceptibility of about -0.20×10^{-6} was obtained. The value for the black chloride approaches that of Milward and co-workers, although somewhat lower. We are, however, convinced of the purity of our product, and the error of our magnetic measurement cannot possibly exceed 2%.

A problem now presents itself regarding the structure of the black chloride. On the basis of the moment value of about 1.73 Bohr, which should result from the presence of one unpaired electron if spin alone be effective, Milward and co-workers suggested the following resonating structures for this compound :

the NO-group in the molecule being responsible for the resonance. The authors based their view on the findings of Brockway and Anderson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 1233), who investigated by electron diffraction the structure of nitroso-carbonyls of cobalt and iron. The metal nitrogen distance in these compounds was found to be somewhat less than the sum of their single bond radius and the internuclear distance of the nitroso-group was intermediate between those for double and triple bonds. Brockway and Anderson, therefore, represented the nitrosyl metal carbonyls in accordance with the resonating electronic structures

Milward and co-workers assume that the bivalent cobalt atom in I becomes univalent by receiving an electron from the nitrogen atom of the NO-group, which then co-ordinates with

the metal atom by sharing a pair of its own electrons. In structure II, it is believed that a normal co-valency is formed between the cobalt and the nitrogen atom in which each atom contributes one electron to the shared pair besides the co-ordination bond due to a pair of electrons supplied by the nitrogen atom. The primary valency of the cobalt atom in this case changes to three. Such an explanation is far from a happy one. In the first place, two structures having univalent and trivalent cobalt respectively cannot resonate as they do not possess the same number of unpaired electrons, which is one of the fundamental conditions for resonance. Secondly, if we assume that they have the same number of electrons, their magnetic moments must be the same.

The moment value of 3.65 Bohr magnetons for the black chloride, obtained by Fraser and Long, is too high and need not be seriously considered. The authors themselves are doubtful about its correctness, and attribute the high value to possible errors in measurement due to the employment of a weak field and also to the presence of 5 mols of water of hydration in their specimen. It is well-known that the black chloride is very unstable in the moist state and changes readily with decomposition into the red form.

It is, however, difficult to choose between the values of 1.66 Bohr magnetons reported by Milward and co-workers and 1.5 Bohr obtained by us. The former represents the concordant results of measurement on different and presumably pure specimens of the substance extending over a wide range of temperature, -195° to 85° ; the latter was based on the measurement of the purest specimen possible.

If we accept Pauling's structure for NO-molecule with a three electron bond, the structure the black complex can be represented as $[(\overset{\ominus}{N})_5Co:N\equiv O:]^{++}$; the Co-N bond may also share a double bond character by resonance, if an unshared pair of electrons from one of the 3-d orbitals of the Co atom is utilised for the formation of an additional co-ordination bond. We have already seen that the cobalt is obviously in the cobaltous state in this octahedral sixfold complex. If this be of the penetration type with d^9-s-p^3 hybrid bonds, then one of the 3-d electrons must be promoted to the 4-d level (*cf.* Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 83, 1367) in order to make two 3-d orbitals available for bond formation. This will evidently increase the energy of the molecule, and, it is well known, all cobaltous complexes of the penetration type are mostly unstable. This promoted and unbalanced electron may have its spin either parallel or anti-parallel to that of the odd electron of the three electron bond in the NO-group. In the former case the molecule will have a paramagnetic moment of 2.82 Bohr magnetons corresponding to the presence of two unpaired electrons, if spin alone be effective and the orbital moments be completely quenched by interaction with the field of neighbouring atoms and ions. In the latter it will be diamagnetic. Both these states, triplet and singlet, are possible, one representing the normal and the other the excited state of the molecule. The energy difference between the two states in an unstable molecule like this may not, however, be great, and both may exist side by side giving rise to an equilibrium depending upon temperature, influence of light, method of its preparation and purity of the product. A high θ -correction or temperature variation of the magnetic moment of the black chloride, observed by Milward and co-workers, furnishes an evidence in support of this view. The molecule may accordingly give an intermediate moment value of 1.7 to 1.5 Bohr magnetons as actually observed by Milward and co-workers, as well as by ourselves.

The diamagnetic character of the red salt can be easily explained on the basis of a trivalent cobalt in the complex, resulting from the transference of an electron from bivalent cobalt to

the nitrogen atom of the NO-group. The latter thus behaves as an electronegative radical like CN^- or Cl^- and forms a negative NO^- ion, which then coordinates with the central cobalt atom by sharing a pair of its own electrons. As already pointed out by Milward and co-workers it is therefore no longer necessary to assume a dimeric formula for the red salt.

EXPERIMENTAL

FIG. 1

Nitroso-pentammine Cobalt Chloride (black).—Scherring's nickel-free cobalt chloride (12 g.) was dissolved in 25 c.c. of water and cooled in ice. This was added to about 60 c.c. of well cooled concentrated ammonia. The mixture was then filtered. The filtrate was introduced into the funnel A of Kapsenberg's filtering apparatus (Fig. 1) from which air was previously replaced by pure nitric oxide. The gas was passed through the solution for about three hours. The entire apparatus was kept cooled by wrapping it with a piece of cloth soaked constantly with ice-water. A large quantity of shining black crystals of the compound separated from the solution. The current of NO was stopped after about three hours and a stream of H_2 gas was introduced through B. The mother-liquor was then removed by filtration, applying suction at C. The crystals were now washed successively with cold absolute alcohol and dry ether (over met. Na) introduced through E. The crystals were dried on the filter-bed in the current of hydrogen. The product was kept in a stoppered weighing bottle over $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator placed inside a refrigerator. {Found: N, 34.21; Co, 24.13; Cl, 28.87. $[ON.Co.(NH_3)_5]Cl_2$ requires N, 34.30; Co, 24.08; Cl, 29.0 per cent}. $D_4^{25} = 1.7380$.

The substance decomposes in water with evolution of oxides of nitrogen and separation of cobaltous hydroxide. In moist air-free CO_2 it changes slowly into pink cobaltous carbonate and ammonium chloride. When treated with water in the absence of air, blue cobaltous hydroxide is produced.

Magnetic Susceptibility

Susceptibility measurements were made according to Guoy's method in a magnetic balance with a maximum field of $10 \cdot 16 \times 10^3$ Gauss produced by a saturation current of 5 amperes. The substance was weighed in a specially designed glass-stoppered tube. The description of the measurement tube, details of the magnetic balance and the method of measurement were given in a previous paper (cf. Ray and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 323).

The mass susceptibility was calculated according to the formula:

$$\chi_s = \frac{2l \times m'}{m \times H^2 \times 1.019} + \chi_v/d_s$$

where l = length of the column of the substance in the tube in cm.,

m = weight of the substance in g.,

H = maximum field strength in gauss,

m' = change in weight in milligrams of the substance,

d_s = density of the substance,

χ_v = volume susceptibility of air,
 T = temperature of measurement (absolute).

$$\chi_{rv} = \frac{2.52 \times 10^{-3}}{T^3}$$

In the present experiment :—

$$l = 10.7, m' = 4.27, m = 0.3013, H = 10.16 \times 10^3, d_s = 1.738, T = 301.$$

Hence $\chi_E = 2.885 \times 10^{-6} + 0.016 \times 10^{-6}$ (air) = 2.901×10^{-6} .

and $\chi_m = 2.901 \times 10^{-6} \times 245 = 710.7 \times 10^{-6}$.

Correction for diamagnetism :—

$$-\chi_a \times 10^6 \dots \dots \text{Co}^{++} = 12.8, \text{Cl}^- = 22.0, \text{ (corrected Pascal's value).}$$

$$\text{NH}_3 = 15.0 \text{ (from corrected Pascal's value of N and H).}$$

$$\text{NO} = 10.2 \text{ (from corrected Pascal's value of N and O).}$$

The value for Co^{++} has been assumed to be equal to that for Zn^{++} (as given by Kido's measurement, because of approximate equality of their ionic radii).

The total diamagnetic correction = $+142.0 \times 10^{-6}$. We have not considered any constitutive correction for the complex formation itself as has been done by Milward and co-workers. This is a factor of doubtful value.

Therefore, $\chi_a = (710.7 + 142.0) \times 10^{-6} = 852.7 \times 10^{-6}$. Hence $\mu_s = 2.84 \sqrt{852.7 \times 10^{-6} \times 301} = 1.44$.

If θ correction of -39.9 , as given by Milward and co-workers, is inserted, μ_s becomes 1.53 .

The value found by Milward and co-workers is $\mu_w = 8.32$ or $\mu_s = 1.664$.

Nitroso-pentammine Cobalt Nitrate (red).—Cobalt nitrate (17.5 g.) was dissolved in 22 c.c. of boiling water and then treated with 80 c.c. of concentrated ammonia. The mixture was left in the cold for 12 hours and then a stream of pure NO was passed through it in absence of air. The red crystals, that separated, were filtered and recrystallised twice from hot water. The product was finally dried in air. {Found: N, 36.93; Co, 19.23. [ON.Co.(NH₅)₅] (NO)₂, 0.5 H₂O requires N, 36.48; Co, 19.21 per cent.]}

Magnetic susceptibility

l	m'	m	$\chi_E \times 10^6$	
9.2 cm.	1.50 mg.	1.306g	-0.2010	cf. $\chi_E \times 10^6 = -0.109$ (Ray and Bhar).
8.3 "	1.23 "	0.9694g	-0.2004	and -0.19 and -0.11 (Milward and co-workers).

The values correspond to measurement in air at the room temperature (28°).